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Shear-dominated processes in sheet metal forming

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ABSTRACT

Many critical manufacturing processes in sheet metal forming are characterized by shear-dominated mechanisms. By clearly defining how shear-dominated processes can be classified based on stress triaxiality and the Lode parameter, this paper provides an overview of their characteristics and challenges in sheet metal forming. Based on the distinction into in-plane and out-of-plane shear-dominated processes and an introduction to the mechanical fundamentals of shearing mechanics, the topics of testing and measurement methods, simulation, and tooling are discussed. Finally, concepts and principles are illustrated with specific application examples. The paper concludes with open topics and upcoming challenges.

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1. Introduction and categorization

Shear-dominated manufacturing processes are a central class of operations in sheet metal forming, critical for producing many high-quality components with dedicated geometries and properties [125]. Shear-dominated deformation refers to a mode of material deformation where shear stresses or shear strains are the primary contributors to the overall stress or strain state in a material [43,215,324]. In this condition, the continuum analogy of relative sliding or tangential movement of material layers predominates over other deformation mechanisms, such as those driven by normal stresses (tensile or compressive) or bending [19,111].

The relative motion between adjacent planes within a material is a key feature of many sheet metal forming manufacturing processes, such as spinning [135], ironing [267], or blanking and cutting [45], where it, for example, controls material flow [246], strain localization [8], and fracture initiation [317]. Despite its relevance, there is no definite definition of shear-dominated deformation, in either mechanics or in the materials processing literature, but rather a loose determination based on the components of the stress tensor or the strain tensor, e.g., in [211] Table 1.2 provides a tool-based differentiation of processes related to induced stresses.

1.1. Structure of the paper

The paper's structure ensures a comprehensive analysis of shear-dominated processes, for which a definition is introduced in Section 1.1. The paper's focus on sheet metal forming is outlined in Section 1.2. Chapter 2 establishes the mechanics of shearing, which delivers

the profound basis for classification. Chapter 3 uses the theoretical basis to examine experimental characterization techniques. Chapter 4 concerns challenges and contemporary strategies for simulating these complex processes. To facilitate the transition from theory to industrial practice, Chapter 5 provides an overview of tooling requirements and solutions. Chapter 6 illustrates the concepts discussed by selected industrial applications. Chapter 7 provides open research questions and future challenges.

1.2. Definition of shear dominance

This paper introduces a clear definition of shear dominance based on the stress state using the stress triaxiality η and the Lode parameter $\bar{\theta}$, which quantify the relative magnitudes and orientations of the principal stresses (see Chapter 2 for details).

Defining shear-dominated manufacturing processes based on stress conditions (stress tensor) rather than strain conditions (strain tensor) offers several advantages regarding clarity, consistency, and applicability to process design and analysis, see, e.g., the German standard DIN8580 (DIN 8582 to 8587). Here are key arguments supporting a stress-based definition in contrast to a strain-based definition in the context of metal forming:

- Applied stresses govern material deformation
 - The boundary value problems in metal forming are typically driven by directly or indirectly applied stresses, where these stress conditions dictate how the material flows or fractures [82].
 - Stress-based criteria are process-independent and hence, independent of the specific deformation history or material response [280]. This makes it applicable across a range of processes and materials.

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- Universality of stress-based parameters
 - The quantification by accepted metrics, such as triaxiality, to describe shear-dominated states is possible [180].
 - These parameters are widely applicable across metal forming processes and beyond. They are readily available in FEM simulations [327].
- Challenges of strain-based definitions
 - Strain states are path-dependent and vary based on deformation history, complicating their use as a universal descriptor for shear-dominated processes [127].
 - Strain behavior depends heavily on material-specific properties, making strain-based definitions less generalizable across different materials and processes [111].
 - Strain-based definitions are less effective in capturing shear-dominated behavior in localized regions where strain distributions can be highly non-uniform [138].

Hence, a stress-based definition of shear-dominated processes offers a more robust, universal, and practical framework compared to strain-based definitions. By leveraging parameters like stress triaxiality and Lode angle, stress-based definitions provide precise and consistent means to describe shear conditions. The proposed criterion is based on an elliptical contour D in the Lode parameter - triaxiality domain, defining a shear-dominated neighborhood around the pure shear point:

$$D = \left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{\theta}}{\bar{\theta}_0}\right)^2 \leq 1 \quad (1.1)$$

Here, η_0 and $\bar{\theta}_0$ describe the permissible deviations from the pure shear point, which are set to $\eta_0 = 0.2$ and $\bar{\theta}_0 = 0.3$, reflecting the perceived spatio-temporal mean values and variances in patterns of the Lode parameter - triaxiality domain of forming processes reviewed during the preparation of the paper (see also supplementary material). $D \leq 1$ defines a region where shear stress is the primary driver of

deformation, with minimal tensile or compressive dominance and nearly equal magnitudes of the intermediate and maximum (or minimum) principal stresses. Inequality (1.1) gives a precise definition for identifying shear-dominated processes in metal forming.

1.3. Focus on sheet metal

This paper focuses on sheet metal processing, where shear-dominated processes can be broadly categorized into in-plane and out-of-plane loading modes, reflecting the directionality of the stresses relative to the sheet plane [192]. In-plane processes, such as spinning [135], ironing [267], and equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) [24], involve deformation primarily within the sheet's plane. Conversely, out-of-plane processes, including processes such as blanking [45] and interlocking [41] induce stresses perpendicular to the sheet plane. Fig. 1 provides an overview of triaxiality and Lode parameter data densities from literature (see supplementary material), serving as a basis for categorization.

1.3.1. Out-of-plane

Out-of-plane shear-dominated processes, such as blanking, fine-blanking, and interlocking, are characterized by highly localized deformation concentrated along narrow shear bands near the interface between the punch, die, and sheet material [106]. These processes primarily involve complex stress states with significant components of shear stresses acting perpendicular to the sheet plane [301]. The deformation is initiated by the application of high shear stresses that exceed the material's yield strength, followed by a progression of localized plastic flow [275].

1.3.2. In-plane

In-plane shear-dominated processes in sheet metal forming, such as ironing, spinning, and roll forming, are characterized by incremental deformation mechanisms that facilitate significant reductions in

Fig. 1. Ranges of triaxiality and lode parameter values for different sheet metal forming processes according to the references given in the supplementary material to categorize shear-dominated processes by means of data density. (ECAP: Equal channel angular pressing, TPIF, Two-point incremental sheet metal forming; SPIF, Single-point incremental sheet metal forming).

sheet thickness while maintaining control over material flow [191,204]. These processes involve shear stresses acting predominantly within the sheet's plane, combined with compressive and tensile stresses that drive material elongation and thinning. Incremental deformation occurs progressively, with localized plastic zones advancing through the material in small steps, allowing for gradual thinning without inducing catastrophic failure [267]. Stress triaxiality in these processes remains relatively low, promoting ductile behavior and delaying the onset of fracture, while the Lode parameter often approaches values indicative of shear-dominant stress states.

2. Mechanics

This chapter provides an overview of the mechanical principles of shear deformation, laying the theoretical basis for the paper.

2.1. Shear and triaxiality

Understanding the interplay between shear deformation, stress triaxiality, and the Lode angle is essential for predicting material behavior under various loading conditions. These factors significantly influence the yielding, plastic flow, and fracture mechanisms of materials. Simple shear and pure shear are commonly used to describe shear deformation. However, actual deformation often deviates from these idealized conditions due to complexities such as normal stresses and rotations. Consequently, several approximations have been developed to better represent real-world shear tests. In addition, simple shear is also not equal to pure shear, and the relation between these two will be clarified below.

In ideal simple shear (state (a) in Table 1), parallel planes within a material slide relative to each other without any volume change. The corresponding deformation gradient is inherently non-symmetric, differentiating it from pure shear. In the small deformation regime, the infinitesimal strain tensor captures only the symmetric part of the deformation gradient. As a result, simple shear (a) and pure shear (f) yield the same strain and stress tensors, despite having different deformation gradients. However, experimental realizations of simple shear often deviate from this idealized condition due to additional deformation components, such as normal stresses or boundary-induced rotations. To approximate these experimental observations, three typical deformation states are summarized in Table 1. State (b) introduces uniaxial perturbations along one axis, simulating axial strains due to boundary conditions; state (c) extends this concept to a more general form, allowing independent perturbations along all three axes; state (d) approximates the ideal simple shear using a polar decomposition, explicitly separating the deformation into a symmetric stretch and a rigid body rotation. This form is beneficial for analyzing the rotational contribution within the overall kinematic field. For a more comprehensive review of the simple shear cases and their applications, readers are referred to [111].

The definition of pure shear is that there is no rotation of the principal axes, where deformation is coaxial and proportional [50]. Two extreme cases can fulfill this definition, states (e) and (f) in Table 1, with respect to the shear deformation γ , or by imposing equal and opposite principal stresses and strains [51]. These two states are mathematically related by a 45° rotation of the principal axes. Comparing state (f) with simple shear (a) helps to elucidate the intrinsic rigid-body rotation.

Table 1 Shear kinematics under shear loading conditions; (a) ideal simple shear; (b) shear-tension; (c) realistic shear; (d) general 3D shear; (e) tension-compression pure shear; (f) kinematic pure shear. (2D cases and more details about the precondition can be found in [111]).

Deformation state	Deformation gradient	Infinitesimal strain tensor	Cauchy stress tensor

Fig. 2. Equivalent strain; (a) coaxial; (b) work conjugate; (c) comparison of two cases [50].

Simple shear can be split into pure shear and rotation, as shown in Fig. 2(a). Eq. (2.1) describes the well-known relation between simple shear and pure shear deformations, where F_γ represents the simple shear deformation gradient, $1 + \varepsilon_\gamma$ the pure shear deformation gradient and ω_γ corresponds to rotation:

$$F_\gamma = 1 + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \gamma & 0 \\ \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \gamma & 0 \\ -\gamma & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = 1 + \varepsilon_\gamma + \omega_\gamma \quad (2.1)$$

One of the main mechanics applications of shear deformation is to derive stress-strain curves as an alternative to tensile tests, because it avoids necking in uniaxial tensile tests. The primary shear type for these tests is simple shear, for which the equivalent stress and strain must be calculated. Under the assumptions of the Mises yield criterion and that the normal stresses are neglected in simple shear, the equivalent stress becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_{VM} &= \sqrt{3}\sigma_{12} = \sqrt{3}\tau \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + (\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})^2 + 6(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{23}^2 + \sigma_{31}^2)}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

However, the calculation of equivalent stress depends on the yield criterion and will deviate from Mises plasticity when stress-state dependent or anisotropic plasticity behavior is evident. On the other hand, the formula for equivalent strain varies based on different underlying assumptions, as shown in Fig. 2(b) and (c), which represent the prerequisite of coaxial (pure shear) and not coaxial (simple shear) separately. The concept of work conjugate is widely employed in FEM analysis, where conjugate stress-strain pairs ensure energetic consistency in numerical formulations. The coaxial equivalent strain

Fig. 3. Processing of shear stress-strain curves and their application in describing material plasticity, anisotropy, and cyclic shear response [100,105,243,321].

is frequently reported by digital image correlation (DIC) software, regardless of the loading condition, due to its generality and simplicity [111]. The error can be neglected when the major strain is less than 0.5, as shown in Fig. 2(d).

The determination of shear strain and stress from experiments is discussed in detail in many works [228,268,322]. Fig. 3 illustrates obtaining a shear stress-strain curve with equations for the shear stresses and strains for the planar simple shear and in-plane torsion conditions. The results of recent tests also go beyond simple shear stress-strain curves and focus on anisotropic plasticity behavior and material behavior under cyclic shear loading.

Besides the stress and strain tensors, the stress triaxiality and Lode angle are commonly used in mechanics to distinguish the stress states. The stress triaxiality and the Lode angle parameter are defined in Eq. (2.3) and Eq. (2.4), respectively:

$$\eta = \sigma_m \bar{\sigma} = \frac{I_1}{3\sqrt{3}J_2} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\bar{\theta} = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}J_3}{2J_2^{3/2}} \right) \quad (2.4)$$

where σ_m and $\bar{\sigma}$ are the mean stress and von Mises equivalent stress, respectively. J_2 and J_3 are the deviatoric stress invariants.

The geometrical interpretation of the stress state is best illustrated in the Haigh-Westergaard stress space, as shown in Fig. 4(a). In this representation, the state of stress is decomposed into a hydrostatic component along the space diagonal (hydrostatic axis) and a

Fig. 4. (a) Representation of Lode angle in principal stress space [175]; (b) Representation of the Lode angle and Lode parameter [26]; (c) Mohr's circle under normal shear-dominated conditions; (d) Mohr's circle of stress state under simple shear or pure shear conditions.

deviatoric component on the plane perpendicular to it (deviatoric plane). The stress triaxiality η describes the position along the hydrostatic axis relative to the equivalent stress radius, while the Lode angle θ defines the orientation of the stress vector within the deviatoric plane.

While the Lode angle θ provides a geometric definition, various scalar parameterizations exist in the literature to quantify the third stress invariant. Common alternatives include the Lode parameter L (ranging from -1 to 1) [181], the normalized third deviatoric invariant ζ [306]. Fig. 4(b) serves as a conversion map, plotting these alternative “third parameters” against the Lode angle parameter $\bar{\theta}$ adopted in this paper. $\bar{\theta} = 0$ corresponds directly to the shear-dominated generalized plane strain condition. The extremes, ± 1 , correspond to axisymmetric tension and compression.

However, for the Lode angle, there are various alternative parameters available in the literature that can serve as substitutes, such as the normalized deviatoric stress invariant ζ [306], the Lode parameter L [181], and a similar definition of the Lode parameter χ [316]. In this review paper, the Lode angle parameter is adopted, and the conversion of other definitions of the second stress-state parameter is shown in Fig. 4(b). While stress triaxiality represents the hydrostatic pressure the materials are subjected to, the Lode angle physically indicates the position of the medium principal stress as shown in Fig. 4(c) in Mohr's circle. When the medium principal stress is equal to the average of the maximum and minimum principal stresses, the Lode angle parameter is zero, which is referred to as the generalized plane-strain condition. Both simple shear and pure shear stress states are specific conditions of the generalized case when stress triaxiality is zero, as illustrated in Fig. 4(d).

2.2. Out-of-plane: localization and adiabatic heating

Shear operations are widely used in material processing to shape, cut, or deform materials by applying opposing forces that induce shear stress along a defined plane. Shear with a triaxiality of zero implies that plastic deformation is purely deviatoric. Therefore, shear-dominant forming processes are highly efficient in terms of the forces required. It is essential to understand that shear can cause both in-plane deformation (within the material's original plane) and

out-of-plane deformation (perpendicular to the cutting plane). Out-of-plane shear is widely used in industrial applications such as sheet metal cutting, shaping, and material separation processes, which include shear cutting, blanking, piercing, notching, and trimming, in which material deformation typically occurs in a highly localized region, leading to fracture along the intended cutting plane [220]. Two critical phenomena that significantly influence material behavior are localization and adiabatic heating. These effects play an essential role in determining failure mechanisms, energy dissipation, and the overall mechanical response of materials during high-strain-rate processes such as shear cutting and blanking [102,115].

Localization refers to the tendency of deformation to concentrate in narrow regions, leading to the formation of shear bands or fracture initiation sites. Material inhomogeneity, stress concentration, and strain rate sensitivity drive this phenomenon. As deformation progresses, localized regions experience intensified strain, resulting in a rapid loss of load-bearing capacity and ultimately leading to failure [16]. Adiabatic heating occurs when plastic work is converted into heat during rapid deformation. At high strain rates, the generated heat has insufficient time to dissipate, leading to a localized temperature rise. This increase in temperature can soften the material, influence its microstructure, and further accelerate the localization process. This interplay between localization and adiabatic heating is crucial in high-speed manufacturing processes, especially for the formation of adiabatic shear bands (ASBs), which are a typical localization of plastic deformation in metallic materials under high-speed impact conditions at a strain rate exceeding 10^3 s^{-1} [102]. The formation of ASBs is considered a result of the interplay between strain hardening, strain-rate hardening, thermal softening, and microstructure softening mechanisms [318]. The specimen geometry and material properties additionally influence the formation of shear bands. Based on the geometry dependency, various specimens have been designed for adiabatic shear instability research, including cylindrical, hat-shaped, and shear-compression specimens [102].

2.3. In-plane: incremental processes

Shear-dominated in-plane processes are pivotal in metal forming when complex geometries and tailored mechanical properties are required. From a mechanical perspective, these processes are characterized by deformation modes in which plastic strain accumulation is governed primarily by shear components under low to moderate stress triaxiality, while tensile thinning and compressive instability are largely suppressed by geometric and contact constraints. Compared with conventional forming processes such as forging or extrusion, shear-dominated processes promote multiaxial material flow through shear-controlled plasticity, thereby improving surface quality and mechanical performance [70,184].

ECAP, rolling, and ironing are three representative shear-dominated in-plane incremental processes. Despite their different process realizations, these techniques share a common deformation mechanism: plastic deformation is incrementally accumulated through the repeated or continuous application of shear-dominated loading. In ECAP and rolling, deformation analysis in the literature primarily emphasizes the evolution and accumulation of shear strain [98], whereas in ironing, the mechanical response is often described in terms of deformation forces and shear stresses arising from frictional contact and tool geometry [57,133,263]. The imposed stress state in ECAP approximates ideal simple shear along the channel intersection plane, allowing large cumulative shear strains to be achieved without significant changes in billet cross section [164,292,333]. The accumulated shear strain is therefore commonly expressed as a function of the total number of passes and the channel semi-angle [263]. In rolling, shear deformation arises from frictional constraints and velocity gradients at the sheet interface, leading to a nonuniform distribution of in-plane shear strain through the thickness [265].

In ironing, plastic flow is dominated by high in-plane shear stresses generated at the interface between die and workpiece, where the shear stress distribution is governed by frictional forces

acting on the lower and upper surfaces [57]. The incremental accumulation of shear-controlled plastic deformation under these conditions underpins the effectiveness of ironing in achieving precise thickness control and enhanced surface quality [2].

3. Testing and measurement methods

Understanding the fundamental behavior of materials under shear-dominated loading conditions is critical for optimizing sheet metal forming processes [111]. The interaction of material properties, stress states, and deformation mechanics governs the quality and performance of the manufactured components, as well as the efficiency and reliability of the processes. Testing and materials science provide the tools to investigate these interactions, enabling the development of predictive models and the selection of materials. This section focuses on three key aspects of testing and materials science in shear-dominated processes. Materials characterization explores the intrinsic properties of sheet metals, such as strength, ductility, anisotropy, and strain-hardening behavior, which influence their performance under shear. Measurement techniques encompass advanced experimental and analytical methods that capture stress-strain responses, failure mechanisms, and deformation patterns at macro- and microscales. Finally, microstructure and pore formation under shear load delves into the microstructural changes induced by shear stresses, including grain orientation, phase transformations, and the initiation and growth of pores or voids that can lead to failure.

3.1. Testing and material characterization

Accurate material testing and characterization are essential for understanding and predicting the behavior of sheet metals under shear-dominated loading conditions in forming processes [111]. Material properties must be identified with precision to model deformation and fracture mechanics accurately, ensuring process efficiency and component quality [253]. This section focuses on the experimental methodologies used for material characterization, including in-plane and out-of-plane shear testing, optimization, and inverse analysis for material parameter identification.

Over time, a variety of shear test geometries have been developed, each tailored to assess specific material properties and behavior under different conditions, see Fig. 5 and Table 2. Most of them are designed for the investigation of formability and fracture mechanisms under shear loading, such as uniaxial Fig. 5 (a–e), torsion Fig. 5 (f–h), multiaxial Fig. 5 (i–l), and out-of-plane shear plates Fig. 5 (m, n).

Fig. 5. Categorization for shear tests: notched shear specimens including several different geometries, such as (a) [20], (b) [228], (c) [28], (d) [197], (e) [268]; torsional shear specimens (f), (g) [46,322], (h) [321]; planar shear specimen (i) [172,199], (j) [80]; cruciform specimen (k) [47], (l) [254]; out-of-plane shear specimen (m) [101]; hat-shaped specimen (n) [214]. (Similar in [111,322]).

3.1.1. In-plane

In-plane shear testing is designed to evaluate the behavior of sheet metals when subjected to shear stresses within their plane

Table 2

A list of references for specimen geometries, where selected geometries are shown in Fig. 5.

Shear test setup	References	Type
Uniax. load.: (a) – (e)	[20,21,28,197,228,268]	In-plane
Torsion: (f) – (h)	[46,287,321,322]	In-plane
Multiax. load.: (i) – (l)	[47,49,80,147,172,199,254]	In-plane
Uniax. load.: (m), (n)	[101,214,332]	Out-of-plane

[323]. Commonly employed methods include shear test specimens, such as those shown in Fig. 5(a)–(e) and (i)–(k), which concentrate shear stresses in specific regions. Another class of tests is torsion tests for sheet metal materials, see specimens Fig. 5(f)–(h). In the in-plane torsion test, true strains of more than 1.0 can be achieved, with values of 3.3 reported for DC04 [291]. Yield curves can be directly computed from experimental measurements according to [174,253,264], with only marginal errors when using the proposed specimen geometries [99].

For in-plane shear tests under translational rather than torsional loading conditions, the design of suitable specimen geometries remains a focus. A challenge here is early fracture initiation at the specimen free edges during experiments. In [66], an intermitted testing regime is proposed to overcome this challenge, where the edges are machined after specific displacements have been applied.

3.1.2. Out-of-plane

Out-of-plane shear testing characterizes material behavior under conditions where shear stresses are applied perpendicular to the plane of the sheet. As shown in Fig. 5, in contrast to the in-plane shear test specimen, only a few studies have been reported on direct out-of-plane shear testing.

In [101], a specimen geometry for a sheet metal is proposed, featuring microscopic notches on both sides of the sheet metal plane that enable shear testing in the out-of-plane direction, even in different orientations relative to the rolling direction. A comparison to in-plane shear tests in the study reveals a significant difference in the material shear stress - shear strain curves, which is especially relevant for material modeling in out-of-plane shear-dominated processes, which often rely only on in-plane experiments. For instance, the mechanical behavior and microstructural evolution in rolled magnesium alloy are significantly different between in-plane shear and through-thickness shear [222]. A total of 27 specimens, including in-plane and out-of-plane tests, were applied to characterize the anisotropic plasticity of the aluminum alloy sheet [172].

In [41], an approach for identifying out-of-plane material parameters is presented and compared with in-plane results. The study uses a laboratory blanking setup to determine basic quantities, such as yield stress, using empirical process equations. Despite relying on analytical relations, this study falls into the broad field of inverse material parameter identification [236], which is especially useful in an out-of-plane context for shear-dominated loading conditions, since a direct measurement or calculation of strain and stresses is hardly possible [200]. In inverse analysis, experimental data, such as force-displacement curves or full-field strain data from DIC, are used for numerical simulations or other predictive models. Optimization algorithms, such as genetic algorithms or gradient-based methods, adjust material parameters iteratively to minimize the objective function, typically a difference measure between experimental results and numerical predictions. For instance in [108], out-of-plane material parameters describing fracture behavior during blanking are identified by comparing punch force-displacement curves from experiments and simulations.

3.2. Measurement techniques

Accurate measurement techniques are fundamental for understanding the mechanics of shear-dominated experiments and processes in sheet metal forming. They provide essential data on state

variables such as strains and temperature. This section presents a brief overview of the measurement methodologies used in experiments and processes, with a special focus on deformation and strain measurement, temperature measurement under shear-dominated load, and finally, how stresses are determined.

3.2.1. Deformation and strain measurement

Understanding deformation and strain distribution is crucial for characterizing material behavior during shear-dominated experiments and processes. Traditional methods, such as strain gauges or the estimation of strain based on grip displacements, have been utilized in shear testing [25,100,243,291,323], but given the localized and non-uniform nature of the strains under shear loading, these methods are challenging and often inadequate [42,285].

Optical techniques, such as DIC and speckle interferometry, have become the standard for full-field strain measurement [3,22], which are increasingly being supplemented by data-driven approaches [113,334].

In principle, by analyzing the displacement of the pattern, DIC provides the data to compute a detailed map of strain distribution across the material [231], including regions of localized shear and necking [110]. A prerequisite for subset-based DIC algorithms to resolve shear deformation adequately is the proper formulation of the shape functions [120,261]. A critical aspect for strain computation is the virtual strain gauge size [110]. This is especially critical for shear testing or process monitoring, where usually the resolution compared to the observed deformation phenomena is comparably large [119,142].

For instance, in the survey provided in [110], gauge lengths reported in literature for the evaluation of shear tests are greater than 100 μm , whereas the authors proposed a method to achieve a gauge length of 28 μm . In [112], strain gauge lengths of under 7 μm are used in the analysis of shear cutting processes by adopting global motion estimation approaches for strain measurement, where the strain computation is not done in a subsequent step, but becomes part of the formalized optimization problem for displacement field identification. These methods have also been applied for crack propagation measurement [121] and higher-order spatio-temporal fields (e.g., strain rates, curvatures, and their rates) for shear cutting [114].

A second optical approach used for deformation and strain measurement under shear loading is based on evaluating the rotation of specific markers [305] or grain morphologies [227]. The observed rotation angle may then be used to compute shear strain values, where the gauge length is determined by the length scale of the utilized markers [227]. Especially when measuring fracture strain during shear tests, the gauge length's influence on strain determination is critical. The deformation zone is often localized into a narrow shear band (range of 10 μm –200 μm [142,224]), where its width may be smaller than the gauge length. This leads to a strong dependency of the measured fracture strain on the chosen gauge length, similar to mesh dependency in FEM [101,179]. Despite efforts to achieve convergence through ever-smaller gauge lengths, studies show that fracture strain increases as gauge length decreases, without reaching a clear convergence point. This phenomenon suggests that reported fracture strains may be lower bounds of actual strain at fracture [111].

3.2.2. Temperature measurement

Temperature plays a critical role in many shear-dominated processes, influencing material flow and fracture behavior in sheet materials. Here, the heat generated by plastic dissipation and friction between the material and the tool surface plays a crucial role. Although measurement techniques exist that enable an estimation of maximum temperatures based on temperature-induced material transformations [156,178] or post-process material analysis [34,195], this section focuses on time-resolved techniques.

For an analysis of temperatures during the ironing process, thermocouples have been installed in the tool, with minimal distance to the surface [219]. To measure temperature development during

incremental sheet metal forming and paddle forming, thermocouples were glued to the sheet metal surface [35]. In [159], different methods for contactless temperature measurement during hot spinning are presented, including pyrometers and infrared cameras, which enable effective control of the process temperature. However, to capture the instantaneous temperature rates up to 10^5 K/s that come with the high strain rates up to 10^3 s⁻¹, especially in out-of-plane shear-dominated processes, different sensing concepts operating directly at the interface are necessary [56].

Hence, in [73], a tactile temperature measurement setup is presented that uses the principle of a thermocouple, the Seebeck effect, and applies it to study shear cutting processes. The punch and the sheet metal represent the thermocouple, enabling an in-situ measurement of the dynamic temperature development in pico-seconds during shear cutting.

3.2.3. Stress determination

Determining stress states under shear-dominated loading conditions requires additional considerations, because, in contrast to experiments like the tensile test or a bulge test, the reference frame rotates [59], i.e., during ongoing shear deformation, the principal directions of the strain tensor are not aligned with the principal axis of the stress tensor (no coaxial loading condition). With accumulating deformation, the principal axis of the strain tensor rotates, where (neglecting normal stresses) the direction of the stress tensor remains the same [229], which becomes especially meaningful in the high-strain regimes that shear-dominated processes can reach. In [51], the influence of coaxial vs non-coaxial formulations on stress determination and further fracture loci calibration is elaborated on. Promising alternatives that may overcome the current assumptions and simplifications for stress determinations rely on the solution of the inverse problem based on an underlying predictive model, which may be an FE model [232] or a data-driven model [166], for example.

3.3. Microstructure evolution and pore formation

Grain refinement, texture evolution, phase transformations, and pore formation are microstructural changes highly influenced by shear deformation. This subchapter presents an overview of these topics.

3.3.1. Grain refinement

Grain refinement is a pivotal mechanism in enhancing the mechanical properties of materials, notably strength and hardness. Shear-dominated processes, characterized by substantial shear strains, are particularly effective at reducing grain size. The development of the grain refinement mechanism within the shear-localization area was reported in [102]. The rotation-dynamic recrystallization (RDR) was adopted to explain the grain refinement phenomenon within the shear localization area. Fig. 6(a) shows the mechanism which is divided into four steps: (1) grain rotation, under severe shear strain, grains rotate along specific axes, aligning with the shear direction; (2) fragmentation of grains, grain rotation and shearing cause grains to fragment into smaller units; (3) formation of ultrafine grains, fragmented grains are further subdivided into ultrafine grains with high-angle grain boundaries; (4) stabilization, grain rotation ceases as grains align with the deformation direction, creating a stable microstructure [319].

In actual sheet metal processing, grain refinement also varies slightly. The primary distinction between different ECAP routes lies in the rotation angle applied to the sample between passes [263]. This route variation significantly influences the strain path, leading to different final grain structures, as shown in Fig. 6(b). Each illustration in Fig. 6(d) represents the appearance of the microstructure on the Y plane, the three rows correspond to the conditions after 1, 2, and 4 passes of ECAP, and the three columns represent the appearance when using routes A, Bc, and C, and η is the total angular range for the various slip systems [160]. Fig. 6(c-d) shows the microstructure and selected area electron diffraction patterns of low-carbon steel

Fig. 6. Illustration of grain refinement steps during shear-related deformation. (a) Grain refinement under shear deformation [319]; (b) Model for grain refinement in ECAP [160]; micro-structure of steel processed by (c) DSR and (d) ECAP [107]; (e) Grain refinement steps in the fine-blanking process [61]; (f) Regions composed of nanosized grains in the shear band of steel after blanking [196].

samples processed by DSR (75% thickness reduction) and ECAP (4 passes). It was confirmed that the structures obtained after the DSR and ECAP show similar grain morphology and misorientation [107].

Similar grain refinement phenomena can also be observed during blanking and shear cutting. Fig. 6(e) shows a schematic drawing of its mechanism. The main difference between these two mechanisms is that, in out-of-plane shear, the cell walls form via dislocation movement under high hydrostatic pressure and shear stress [61]. Fig. 6(f) shows the ultra-fine grains in the shear band observed by TEM after fine-blanking, which exhibit a similar grain size and morphology to those formed after in-plane processes [196]. The ultra-fine grain at the sheared edge was reported to significantly influence micro-hardness and magnetization [312].

3.3.2. Texture evolution

In materials science, “texture” refers to the preferred orientation of grains within a polycrystal. The detailed definition and description of each route can be found in the literature [279,281]. Shear-dominated processes, such as rolling and ECAP, significantly influence texture evolution. The nature of texture evolution varies with the crystal structure of the material, see Fig. 7, face-centered cubic (FCC), body-centered cubic (BCC), or hexagonal close-packed (HCP) [284]. For FCC materials, the ideal shear deformation texture consists of $\{001\} \langle 110 \rangle$, $\{111\} \langle 110 \rangle$, and $\{111\} \langle 112 \rangle$ [145].

Fig. 7(a) shows the Al alloy’s (111) pole figure after asymmetry rolling in nine passes with rotation through 180° about ND, RD, and TD axes each pass. Similar shear textures, which can be approximated by $\{001\} \langle 110 \rangle$ and $ND \parallel \langle 111 \rangle$ orientations through the thickness [165]. During severe plastic deformation of BCC materials, the shear texture is characterized by the Goss orientation, $\{110\} \langle 001 \rangle$. Fig. 7(b) shows the (110) pole figure of IF steel after symmetry rolling (SR) and two asymmetric rolling (ASR), which exhibits the typical BCC

Fig. 7. Texture evolution in different materials. (a) (111) pole figure of AA1050 asymmetrical rolled by 75% in nine [165]; (b) (110) pole figures of bcc material after symmetrical rolling and two asymmetrical rolling; (c, d) texture evolution and corresponding density profiles after different ECAP routes for Mg alloy [281].

rolling texture [163]. Compared with the pole figure for SR, a slight tilt about the TD direction toward the driven roll was observed. The ideal orientations formed in HCP materials are fibers B with $\{0001\}$ shear plane and called basal fibers. An intense basal texture was reported to cause the materials to exhibit apparent asymmetry and anisotropy under tension and compression [88]. Therefore, controlling texture is essential for improving their mechanical performance and formability. Fig. 7(c) and (d) display the texture evolution and corresponding density profiles after different ECAP routes for the Mg alloy. It was confirmed that ECAP explicitly influences the maximum pole intensity and distribution of basal planes. On route C, the work-piece is inverted between passes, which may increase dislocation accumulation in shear bands and enhance grain refinement. This may be the reason why the sheet processed on route C shows the weakest texture [281].

3.3.3. Phase transformation

The third-generation advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) have gained significant attention for their ability to balance performance and cost-effectiveness. These steels are categorized into three primary types: TRIP-assisted bainitic ferrite (TBF), quenching and partitioning (QP) steels, and medium manganese (Med-Mn) steels [111].

All these variants are assisted by the transformation-induced plasticity (TRIP) effect, which is dependent on the stress state during deformation [72]. The behavior of retained austenite and its transformation into martensite varies under different loading conditions, influencing the material's mechanical response [123].

The phase transformation rate under shear loading is significantly lower than under other loading conditions, such as uniaxial tension, plane strain, and biaxial tension [32,144]. Fig. 8(a) shows the evolution of volume fraction of retained austenite during deformation under different loading conditions for QP980. The stress-strain response of the material under different loading conditions is therefore strongly influenced by the corresponding phase transformation rates, as shown in Fig. 8(b) [123].

Fig. 8. The deformation-induced phase transformation and related mechanical behavior: (a) the evolution of volume fraction of retained austenite and (b) stress-strain curves under different loading conditions [123].

3.3.4. Pore and micro-crack evolution

Void formation in materials is closely linked to the presence of inclusions [111]. These inclusions and particles, or secondary phases, often have mechanical properties that differ from those of the surrounding material, leading to stress concentrations during deformation. Under shear-dominated processes, these stress concentrations can initiate voids, which may coalesce into micro-cracks and lead to final failure.

The mechanisms of void formation and evolution can be divided into three steps: 1. stress concentration at inclusions and particles or phase boundaries, causing localized stress concentrations; 2. void elongation and rotation under continued shear stress, as shown in Fig. 9(a) [6]; 3. void coalescence into micro-cracks and shear cracks, see Fig. 9(b) [171]. Furthermore, the morphology of voids and subsequent crack evolution is strongly dependent on the specific mode of shear loading [211]. In in-plane shear, voids tend to elongate into

Fig. 9. Void formation and coalescence. (a) Void elongation and rotation under continued shear stress [6]; (b) rolled plate along with the micro-crack orientations, produced during cross-rolling [171]; (c) pores found in the ECAP-processed Cu-1 wt.% Pb alloy [76]. (d-g) microstructure distributed around the shear band as a function of punch penetration [330].

flattened, elliptical shapes aligned with the shear direction, often leading to shear bands rather than open cracking. Conversely, in out-of-plane shear, the material undergoes twisting and tearing deformations, resulting in distinct, often asymmetric, void coalescence patterns and crack surface morphologies. Fig. 9(c) is a TEM figure of ultrafine-grained Cu-1 wt.% Pb alloy deformed by ECAP, where nanopores were observed [76]. Fig. 9 (d–g) shows the microstructure observed by SEM according to different punch penetrations during fine-blanking. A shear band began to form parallel to the punching direction, and shear deformation and localization gradually extended to the entire clearance zone. Finally, micro-voids and micro-cracks around the inclusions propagated along the blanking direction [330].

4. Simulation

Based on the concepts introduced in the previous chapters, this section focuses on the numerical modeling of shear-dominated processes, identifying and addressing the complexities of capturing their inherent challenges. Table 3 consolidates these challenges, leading to specific difficulties summarized in Table 4.

Table 3

Origin of shear-dominated process simulation challenges.

In-plane	Out-of-plane
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Localized plasticity, incremental deformation (I.1) Extended process time and tool displacement (I.2) Thickness-to-area ratio (I.3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High strain localization (shear bands) (O.1) Limited characterization (O.2) High processing speeds (O.3) Material fracture behavior (O.4)
Shared challenges	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Path-dependent strain evolution (S.1) Temperature-driven effects (S.2) Large deformation due to delayed fracture onset (S.3) Microstructural refinement and evolution (S.4) 	

4.1. Numerical challenges in shear-dominated process simulation

The challenges inherent to shear-dominated processes listed above lead to several issues that must be addressed when numerically simulating these processes. Table 4 identifies the numerical issues arising from shear-dominated processes and classifies them into in-plane, out-of-plane, and shared challenges.

Table 4
Numerical challenges of shear-dominated process simulation.

In-plane	Out-of-plane
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale effects (I.1) • Large local strains (I.2) • Computational cost (I.3) • Tribological complexities (I.4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical element distortion (O.1) • Material modeling limitations (O.2) • High heating rate (O.3) • Fracture modeling (O.4)
Shared challenges	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strain-driven FE codes (S.1) • Mesh sensitivity (S.2) • Rate and temperature material dependence (S.3) • Multi-scale simulation (S.4) 	

In-plane shear-dominated process simulations face numerical challenges related to scale, large local strains, and high computational cost [81,296,302,315]. The small thickness-to-area ratio and incremental deformation mechanisms require fine meshing to capture localized plastic zones, increasing computational demand, see Fig. 10 [77,92]. Additionally, extended tool movement and process time add complexity, while tribological effects influence force predictions [71], making accurate simulation more difficult.

Fig. 10. Mesh dependence on the numerically obtained strain localization of a uniaxial compression test [77].

Out-of-plane shear-dominated process simulations are particularly affected by extreme strain localization, severe element distortion, and high heating and loading rates [60,193,259]. Highly concentrated shear bands near the punch-die interface lead to severe mesh deformation, affecting numerical stability [53,330]. In addition, high-rate deformation and material fracture behavior make conventional models unreliable [35,53], while the associated temperature rise further complicates simulation accuracy [73,241].

Furthermore, both in-plane and out-of-plane processes share several numerical challenges, including path-dependent strain evolution, mesh sensitivity, and temperature effects [53,140,198]. Strain localization makes simulations highly dependent on element size and distribution, influencing strain softening behavior [330]. Most FEM codes rely on strain-driven constitutive updates based on accumulated equivalent strain, which can inadequately represent the evolving deformation history and non-coaxiality inherent to shear-dominated processes [1,202]. Additionally, temperature gradients and microstructural changes, such as grain refinement and void formation, add further complexity to the definition of reliable constitutive models [176,293].

4.2. Tools and strategies

To mitigate or overcome these numerical challenges, various tools and strategies exist that enhance simulation accuracy and efficiency. These methodologies focus on improving simulation reliability, thereby enabling a more precise representation of the intricacies inherent to these processes. In the following lines, a compilation of

the most widely used methods is presented, delineating the numerical challenge they mitigate or resolve in brackets in each instance.

4.2.1. Modeling assumptions and simplifications

While shear-dominated processes are inherently characterized by significant plastic work dissipation and adiabatic heating, many numerical frameworks initially adopt an isothermal assumption to reduce computational complexity [62,157] (O.3/S.3 in Table 4). This simplification is often justified in processes where the stroke rate is low enough to allow for thermal conduction into the tooling, or when the primary focus is on kinematic hardening and strain localization patterns rather than thermal softening [188,314]. However, as discussed previously, for a high-fidelity prediction of shear banding and localized ductility, the coupling of thermomechanical solvers is mandatory to account for thermal softening, which destabilizes the material and promotes shear failure.

Classical 2D simplifications, such as axisymmetry, plane strain, or plane stress assumptions, can significantly reduce computational cost, even if they introduce certain inaccuracies [27,218,298]. Combining these simplified models with targeted validation using more detailed simulations is often the most effective strategy for efficient and reliable results (I.1/I.3 in Table 4).

Considering that in the majority of forming simulations, tools are typically regarded as rigid or at least of considerable rigidity in comparison to the workpiece, a conventional method is to alter the reference framework of the procedure to consider the workpiece as stationary [153,271] (even when real processes are in motion). This approach directly reduces the rigid solid displacement of the mesh, thereby easing the numerical computations (I.3 in Table 4). Nevertheless, particular attention must be directed primarily to in-plane operations such as SPIF, where, due to the elevated localized pressure and tool configuration, tool deflection can be essential, and consequently, the implementation of modified coordinate systems could lead to significant errors [23].

Specific industrially prevalent in-plane procedures, such as the ironing method, for instance, exhibit significant numerical complexity [15,103,267]. Consequently, empirical correlations are often used to calibrate tools and predict process outcomes [63,245], reducing computational cost while maintaining acceptable accuracy (I.1/I.3 in Table 4).

4.2.2. Multiscale and surrogate modeling

When simulating manufacturing processes that involve significant local deformation and microstructural evolution, while still requiring full-scale modeling, multiscale modeling is often applied (S.4 in Table 4). In this methodology, macro- and micro-scale simulations are coupled: the macro model provides boundary conditions to the micro model, while the micro model feeds back material behavior to the macro scale [94,188].

Surrogate modeling and AI support multiscale simulations by enhancing computational efficiency and predictive accuracy. Techniques such as Gaussian Process-based models enable rapid predictions of microscopic responses without extensive offline training (I.1/I.3/S.4 in Table 4), thereby reducing the computational cost of FE simulations [249]. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) and physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) approximate stress fields and deformations in metal forming, enabling accurate predictions of process outcomes [208]. Other approaches, such as kernel methods, have also been applied to improve the coupling between scales by learning the interface behavior (I.1/S.4 in Table 4), improving simulation accuracy [309]. However, challenges persist, including the need for standardized methodologies, training data, and maintaining a balance between computational efficiency and model fidelity [187].

Nevertheless, owing to lengthy processing times, in certain cases where microscopic development does not significantly influence material behavior, the most efficient approach is to separate the microscopic and macroscopic evolution (I.1/S.4 in Table 4). A phenomenological law is introduced at the macro level to represent the

average material response, and the resulting outputs can then be used to estimate microstructural changes in a post-processing step [130,154].

4.2.3. Material behavior and fracture mechanics

Beyond the localized phenomena in shear-dominated processes, most out-of-plane shear processes involve high loading rates that, through adiabatic heating, result in significant temperature increases [73]. A representative hardening model (S.3 in Table 4) that incorporates rate- and temperature-dependent effects is the Johnson-Cook model [223]. These models are particularly critical for capturing the formation of ASBs, which are the primary precursors to failure in high-speed blanking or punching. However, these factors influence material hardening and ductile fracture, typically modeled using stress-state-dependent criteria (triaxiality and Lode angle). To address this, various studies have extended these ductile fracture models (O.2/O.4/S.3 in Table 4) to incorporate temperature [36], strain rate [85], or both effects [4]. Yet, these modifications rely primarily on in-plane specimen tests, as characterization methods for out-of-plane specimens remain scarce [101].

Additionally, the high heating rates characteristic of processes like blanking are often overlooked during material characterization (O.3 in Table 4). Parameter identification for the previously mentioned hardening and fracture models can be challenging due to the vast amount of experimental data (O.3/O.4/S.3 in Table 4). The most common methods involve minimizing errors in stress-strain curves [241] and hybrid experimental-numerical approaches that optimize force-displacement curves for hardening models [85]. Similarly, ductile

fracture models are calibrated through the latter approach, targeting either proportional [306] or non-proportional [4] fracture surfaces, see Fig. 11. More recently, AI-driven methods, such as ANNs, have emerged as an alternative for parameter identification with great capacity to handle large datasets and complex loading histories [173].

While phenomenological ductile fracture models have been the primary focus so far, other approaches must also be considered (O.2/O.4/S.4 in Table 4). Micromechanical models, such as Rice & Tracey [247] and Gurson-Tvergaard-Needleman [104], incorporate physical mechanisms such as void nucleation, growth, and coalescence to capture material softening and fracture behavior in ductile materials. In shear-dominated loading, however, traditional void growth models must be modified, as damage often accumulates through void rotation and shearing rather than through hydrostatic expansion, a distinction that is vital for predicting failure in processes such as ECAP or ironing.

Furthermore, non-local and gradient-based models address challenges like mesh dependency (O.1/O.4/S.2 in Table 4) and strain localization (I.2/O.4 in Table 4) by introducing length-scale parameters or additional governing equations. Some examples to be highlighted would be gradient damage models [273], suitable for severe and localized plastic deformation, and phase-field fracture models [233], which accurately capture crack initiation and propagation.

Indeed, crack propagation in shear-dominated processes presents significant numerical challenges, requiring robust modeling techniques to capture initiation and propagation accurately (O.4 in Table 4).

Fig. 11. Fracture response of DP980 steel: (a) Hosford–Coulomb surface for proportional loading; (b–e) equivalent plastic strain to fracture vs. stress triaxiality, Lode angle, strain rate, and temperature. Solid dots: model predictions; solid line ends: experimental fracture initiation [85]. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

In operations like fine-blanking, the precision of the crack path determines the final “clean-cut” depth and the resulting burr height. A traditional approach, such as the kill elements method, removes highly damaged elements once failure criteria are met, though this can lead to numerical instabilities [129]. A more stable option would be node-splitting, which explicitly tracks crack growth by separating nodes at the crack tip, preserving continuity in the remaining structure [122]. More recently developed methods are also available, such as the already mentioned phase-field models, which offer a versatile approach by representing cracks as diffuse interfaces, enabling the natural simulation of complex propagation patterns without predefined paths [233]. Alternatively, the extended FEM (X-FEM) enhances traditional FEM by introducing enrichment functions, allowing cracks to propagate independently of the mesh while maintaining computational efficiency [40].

4.2.4. Contact mechanics

Friction plays a crucial role in shear-dominated processes, directly influencing stress distribution, tool wear, and material flow (I.4 in Table 4). In these applications, interfacial friction acts as a secondary shear source, triggering premature surface localization or significantly altering the trajectory of shear bands. Conventional friction models, such as Coulomb and shear-based laws, often fail to capture the high strain rate, pressure, and temperature effects present in these processes. More advanced formulations, including velocity- and pressure-dependent models such as Filzek’s model and thermomechanical interface laws, provide more accurate predictions by incorporating strain-hardening, lubrication breakdown, and surface roughness effects [207]. For high-pressure applications, such as ironing or fine-blanking, hybrid formulations, such as Zorév’s model, are essential because they differentiate between sticking and sliding zones by limiting frictional shear to the material’s yield strength [276]. Similarly, the Wanheim-Bay model is often employed to account for the evolution of the real contact area under severe plastic deformation [304], filling the gap between simplified laws and the complex interfacial physics of shear-dominated manufacturing.

Machine learning (ML) and physics-informed models are also emerging as powerful tools for refining friction representations in complex contact conditions [190]. Ensuring stable contact interactions in numerical simulations of shear-dominated processes is particularly challenging due to large deformations, high contact pressures, and severe mesh distortions (I.4/O.1/S.2 in Table 4). Inaccurate contact pressure distribution can lead to erroneous triaxiality predictions, which are critical for predicting the onset of shear fracture. Penalty-based contact methods (see Fig. 12), while computationally efficient, can introduce artificial penetrations or unstable force oscillations [31]. The augmented Lagrangian method improves accuracy by iteratively enforcing contact constraints while mitigating numerical instability [97]. Meanwhile, the mortar method offers a more robust approach by ensuring consistent stress transfer across non-matching meshes, which is essential for capturing the sharp stress gradients typical of localized shear bands without introducing numerical artifacts [149].

Fig. 12. Contact penetration fields for different contact modeling accuracies, $\delta = 0.01$ (left) and $\delta = 0.001$ (right) [31].

4.2.5. Element technology and techniques

Element regularization techniques, particularly through the GISSMO [240], have emerged as a pivotal approach in computational mechanics to manage the challenges posed by high local gradients in material behavior (O.4/S.2/S.4 in Table 4). In shear-dominated processes, these techniques are useful for mitigating the mesh-dependence of energy dissipation within narrow shear bands, ensuring that the predicted failure point remains objective regardless of element size.

By integrating solid-shell element formulations [96,225], this method combines the efficiency of sheet formulation with the through-thickness gradient capability of a solid element, maintaining accuracy in simulations of in-plane processes (I.1/I.3 in Table 4). PUFEM (partition of unity FEM) [294] allows efficient handling of localized phenomena without requiring excessive mesh refinement. Furthermore, techniques such as local remeshing and the X-FEM [93,143] with strain gradient considerations, provide additional flexibility and precision in capturing the complex behavior of materials under stress. These remeshing strategies are key for processes involving severe plastic deformation, such as ECAP, where extreme element distortion would otherwise lead to numerical termination or severe loss of accuracy. These advancements collectively support high-fidelity analyses while minimizing computational costs, facilitating in-plane and out-of-plane shear-dominated process simulation (I.2/O.1/O.4/S.2 in Table 4).

5. Tooling

The design of tools is a pivotal factor that influences the precision, efficiency, and quality of shear-dominated processes, thereby bridging the gap between mechanical theory and industrial applications. Challenges differ depending on whether the shearing is applied in or out-of-plane. In out-of-plane processes, the focus is on controlling high local pressures, bending moments, and resulting tool wear. Conversely, in-plane processes require control of tool paths and process forces to prevent error propagation over multiple forming steps. This chapter underscores challenges and solutions for both process categories.

5.1. Tooling for out-of-plane shearing

The working principle of a shear cutting tool is based on the interaction between two cutting edges moving towards each other while maintaining a constant distance under load. As shown in Fig. 13, both cutting edges move relative to each other, maintaining a constant distance between them, called the cutting clearance. Due to forced press ram movement, sufficiently high forces are applied onto the flat

Fig. 13. Forces and moments acting during out-of-plane shearing of sheet metal.

material between both edges until it is separated. The force system of the punching process consists of cutting forces (F_S , F'_S) acting on the punch and die. Consequently, vertically and horizontally acting friction forces (F_V , F'_V) and 1 force components (F_H , F'_H) are induced. Due to the cutting clearance, the cutting forces (F_S , F'_S) generate internal bending moments (M_B , M'_B), which create several challenges for proper shearing [113].

5.1.1. Compensating bending

Achieving high precision in the shearing process requires a tool design that minimizes deviations in part properties and ensures robust and stable material separation. One key challenge is controlling and compensating for the acting bending moment (M_B , M'_B), which induces elastic deformation of the tool components, resulting in inaccurate cut surfaces of the blanks and/or slug. To mitigate these effects, a rigid tool design ensuring a proper alignment of both the punch and the die under load is essential [113].

In addition, precision machining of each tool component, an accurate upper and lower tool guidance system, and a rigid press frame with tight ram guidance help reduce elastic deformation of the tool components and may help avoid horizontal offset or tilting of the upper tool. In addition, bending moments can lift the blank during shearing, requiring sufficient clamping force through a stripper plate or part holder. The bending moment also causes plastic deformation of the blank, i.e., undesired blank distortion, which often requires additional flattening of the produced product in subsequent manufacturing steps [242].

In the transition within the mobility sector towards electromobility, high-precision shearing of thin foils ($s < 50 \mu\text{m}$) has emerged as a pivotal element in the fabrication of pouch cells and bipolar plates [34]. The ability to achieve cutting clearances of several micrometers demands a robust, comprehensive system to maintain them, thereby ensuring the consistency and quality of the production process.

5.1.2. Compensating wear

Force application in shearing is highly localized, occurring within the contact area between the active tool surfaces and the material. The vertical (F_V , F'_V) and horizontal (F_H , F'_H) force components, as shown in Fig. 13, significantly influence the quality of the cut edge of manufactured parts. Additionally, frictional forces, including vertical (μF_N , $\mu F'_N$) and horizontal components (μF_V , $\mu F'_V$) do affect tool wear and energy consumption. Wear in metal forming is primarily the result of repeated interactions between the tool and the workpiece under conditions of high local pressure, high temperature, or inappropriate surface topologies [10]. The type of wear, which may manifest as abrasion, adhesion, surface breakdown, or tribo-chemical reactions, describes the physical and chemical interactions within the tribological system's contact zone. In contrast, the mechanisms of wear, including sliding wear, impact wear, and two-body abrasion, define the kinematics of the interacting friction partners [69]. Interactions of different wear types and mechanisms produce distinct wear appearances such as roundness deviations, scratches, pits, and craters. Fig. 14 shows those defects after 10^5 and 10^6 strokes. Sliding wear, impact wear, and three-body abrasion are key wear mechanisms in blanking. Sliding wear is driven by relative tool–sheet motion under normal pressure and is often accompanied by adhesion and tribochemical reactions promoted by long contact times and high stresses. Three-body abrasion occurs when loose particles enter the contact and act as abrasive wedges, producing grooves on the tool surface during sliding. Impact wear results from repeated shock loading of the tool against the sheet, leading to cumulative damage, surface fatigue, and local fracture. These mechanisms reduce dimensional accuracy, shorten tool life, and generate surface defects on parts. Mitigation includes wear-resistant tool materials and surface treatments, effective lubrication, and process parameter optimization to lower frictional and thermal loads [68].

By selecting materials with superior wear resistance, such as high-speed steels (HSS) or powder metallurgy (PM) tool steels [64,307], the longevity and performance of shear-cutting punches can be

Fig. 14. Wear evolution during punching with different punch materials. [308]. (HSS: High speed steel; REX: CPM Rex 76, CP: Carbide punch).

substantially improved, reducing maintenance and operational costs [185].

In addition to reduced friction between tool and material, adequate lubrication aids in achieving higher precision by facilitating material flow and reducing the likelihood of defects such as galling [205]. New tribo-systems aim to replace hazardous lubricants, such as chlorinated paraffin oils, with more sustainable alternatives [30]. Solid lubrication has been identified as a method of reducing friction and wear [132]. The in situ solid lubrication of carbon-supersaturated (CS-) steel dies has been proposed to reduce friction and adhesive wear, for example, to minimize galling during the fine-blanking process of titanium [9], see Fig. 15.

Fig. 15. Comparison of fine-blanking punches after punching titanium. Conventional punch (left); carbon-supersaturated punch (right) [9].

Also coatings, such as DLC (Diamond-like carbon) and those applied by PVD (physical vapor deposition) and CVD (chemical vapor deposition) [248] are regularly used in tooling, where recent studies indicate that multilayer approaches achieve the best results [128,299].

Mechanical peening and hammering improve fatigue strength and reduce surface wear through compressive residual stresses. Furthermore, the recesses created can serve as beneficial lubricant pockets [277]. Using a picosecond laser to apply an optimized dimple pattern and geometry can reduce friction by up to 50% and increase tool life by 200% [150].

5.1.3. Process monitoring for high stroke rate production

Shearing of sheet metal often runs up to ~ 3000 strokes per minute. The rapid cycles and complex machine–process interactions during ramp-up and serial production are complex to monitor,

underscoring the need for advanced systems that track and analyze parameters for fault detection, tool protection, and part quality. ML leverages historical and real-time data to improve anomaly detection and prognostics, often with greater adaptability and lower cost than traditional sensors [137,230], previously accessible only via time-intensive methods [126].

Soft sensors now document cutting-edge wear of punches and dies in real time, such as wear states from punch force signals [158] boosted with additional sensors [213], or image-based classification [201]. Fig. 16 compares images of a worn punch captured during a fast-running shearing process, the mask generated from them, and the prediction made by an ML model [258].

Fig. 16. Comparison of the unprocessed image to the ground truth and prediction of the FCN [258]. (Black: Background, Green: Unworn area, Red: Contamination, Blue: Grooves, Yellow: Surface Spalling). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

Due to the high industrial relevance of the cutting surfaces of sheared components, numerous publications focus on the inline monitoring of their resulting cutting surface quality, for example, based on punch force profiles with an ML model also trained on FEA results [256]. In fine-blanking, eddy-current NDT could be used to predict the tearing behavior of gear-shaped 42CrMo4+A components [221].

Also mechanical properties of various steel grades have been identified based on the punch force signals via ANNs [255] and by additionally using advanced feature engineering methods [95].

5.1.4. Improving shear cut surface

The simple design of shearing tools has facilitated the evolution of a diverse range of separation processes, primarily driven by the varying requirements of industrial practice regarding the shear cut surface defined in VDI 2906 [295].

For many components, high clean-cut portions are required. One strategy to increase the clean-cut relies on superimposing compressive stresses during shearing, extending plastic deformation by stabilizing the triaxiality in the compressive domain, also for deep punch penetration.

The evolution of the stress state within the shearing zone for conventional (red) and fine-blanking (green) is depicted in Fig. 17 through a Mohr's circle representation. Within this framework, the inclined envelope (a) signifies the failure locus dictated by the Mohr-Coulomb criterion, which accounts for the strength-differential (SD) effect. This asymmetry in material behavior underscores why metallic materials exhibit a larger elastoplastic regime under compression than under uniaxial tension. Mohr's circle for conventional blanking (red) enters the plastic regime at the yield threshold; however, because it lies in a region of low compressive or even tensile stress, it quickly reaches the shear fracture limit. This leads to early crack propagation and a predominantly fractured surface. In contrast, Mohr's circle for fine-blanking (green) is situated in the compressive stress region. Here, the Mohr-Coulomb envelope (a) is significantly higher, allowing the material to undergo extensive plastic deformation without fracturing, which results in a sheared surface with a larger clean-cut portion.

Fig. 17. Mohr's diagram for comparing conventional to fine-blanking. These conditions include the shear yield limit (a), the shear fracture limit (b), conventional blanking (c), and fine-blanking (d) [17].

Fine-blanking is a triple-action process that yields near-100% clean-cut portions by superimposing compressive stresses on the shear zone [162], achieved by plastically indenting a V-shaped ring into the sheet, using minimal clearances (<0.5% of thickness) [295], and employing a counter-holder to prevent plastic deflection [269]. Different adaptations of fine-blanking have been proposed following the general idea of stabilizing the stress triaxiality in the compressive domain, for example, via small clearances and intentional edge rounding on the punch (piercing) or die (blanking), supported by high part-holder forces [125], or solely by dimensional modification of punching tool edges [264,289].

Compressive stress superposition has also been achieved using a cross-elastic part holder that applies a compressive force in the sheet metal plane through static friction in addition to the vertical force to fix the sheet metal, see Fig. 18 [44].

Fig. 18. One- or double-sided Z-shaped part-holders for compressive tensile stress superposition[44].

Adiabatic or quasi-adiabatic blanking provides an alternative method for improving the cut surface quality of sheet-metal components through a different mechanism. This process is distinguished by tool velocities exceeding 8 m/s, local strain rates exceeding 10^3 s^{-1} , and processing times shorter than 2 ms [250]. The interaction between thermal softening and strain localization establishes a self-reinforcing mechanism that forms an ASB within the shear zone. [313,326] The resulting adiabatic cut surface is characterized by a near-perpendicular orientation, the absence of burrs, and a fine-textured fracture zone [250]. Nevertheless, achieving such high cutting velocities with conventional industrial presses is often unfeasible, and dedicated hydraulic presses, specialized equipment such as drop hammers, or electromagnetic cutting devices must be used [239]. Electromagnetic cutting, based on

electromagnetic forming, employs a pulsed magnetic field to apply Lorentz forces to conductive workpieces. Since no mechanical contact is needed, common issues such as cold welding and slivers are eliminated [239].

Small burr heights or burr-free edges may be another requirement on the cut surface to reduce injury risk, prevent tool damage and excessive wear, or avoid coating defects. Counter-cutting is widely used in mass production [162], but requires experiments to determine penetration depth and cutting clearance as functions of material properties and sheet thickness [125]. Two-stage notch-cutting is an alternative process that utilizes a notch to initiate separation before burr formation [252].

Edges of the shear-cut sheet metal component show reduced formability in subsequent forming processes, which is attributed to induced hardening and damage. Two-stage cutting and shaving on single-acting presses yields dimensionally accurate internal or external shapes with superior cut-surface quality [311]. The component is first pre-punched or pre-cut; in the shaving stage a narrow rim of the contour is removed, improving the cut surface. Shaving clearance is typically 8–19% of sheet thickness, and progressive-die designs must ensure precise part positioning; chip evacuation can also constrain process stability [155]. Shaving increases the smooth-cut portion and improves residual forming capacity versus conventional cut edges [257].

5.2. Tooling for in-plane shearing

In-plane shearing is a family of incremental forming processes in which the primary deformation mechanism is governed by shear stresses acting within the sheet's plane. Unlike conventional deep-drawing techniques, which rely on tensile or compressive forces to drive material flow, these processes use controlled, localized shear to shape thin-walled structures. This unique deformation mode offers several advantages in terms of dimensional accuracy, surface quality, and flexibility; however, it also poses specific challenges.

5.2.1. Error propagation in-plane shearing

The incremental nature of in-plane shear processes renders the accumulation of errors and inaccuracies inevitable [135]. Error propagation turns small, seemingly negligible inaccuracies into significant defects by amplifying them across multiple deformation steps. Geometric inaccuracies, surface defects, thinning, cracking, and wrinkling [58,235,270] are all potential outcomes if errors in tool paths, material behavior, or process conditions aren't managed [39,58,84,90]. This is particularly critical for industries requiring high-precision components, such as aerospace and medical device manufacturing [79]. Tool wear is also an inevitable factor in-plane shearing, especially when processing high-strength alloys [74]. Over time, wear-induced changes in tool geometry, surface roughness, and clearance between tooling can progressively degrade the quality of parts [131,183]. Monitoring and compensating for tool wear is crucial to minimizing error propagation.

5.2.2. Process control strategies for in-plane shearing

Effective process control is essential for achieving consistent, high-quality outcomes in-plane shearing processes. Contrary to conventional processes, where adjustments are frequently executed post-process, in-plane shearing incorporates real-time monitoring and feedback mechanisms for control [11,135].

In [11], it is demonstrated that closed-loop control in rolling is dominated by three domains: center-line thickness (or gauge) of the strip, the distribution of residual stress and thickness (flatness and profile) across the width of cold-rolled strip, and the microstructure [11]. The landscape has undergone a shift from expert-based control to autonomous systems [5,300,329,331]. While the core physical domains remain, the methodology has transitioned from empirical models to PINNs [242,283]. These architectures integrate partial

differential equations for heat conduction and phase transformation kinetics directly into the control loss function, ensuring that AI-driven cooling strategies remain thermodynamically consistent. Furthermore, the sensing constraints identified in [11] have been mitigated by the industrialization of Laser-Ultrasonic Sensing (LUS), which allows for non-contact, real-time monitoring of internal residual stresses and online grain size evolution [67]. With Digital Twin frameworks for high-fidelity rolling mill simulation [282], the control objective has expanded. Modern systems now optimize the entire thermomechanical history to guarantee specific mechanical properties, such as yield strength and elongation, as the primary closed-loop output [168,303,320].

The deformation and failure behavior of incremental sheet metal forming, such as SPIF, can be well described by membrane stresses [191,192]. Nevertheless, controlling the triaxiality and through-thickness deformation in the stationary process with respect to the shear domain is critical [134,183]. Process control and path planning methodologies have evolved from rudimentary toolpath generation [33,182,189,244] over knowledge-based systems [117,118] to the implementation of integrated, online closed-loop systems [13,109,116]. Process control is the primary means of addressing the inherent problems concerning incremental forming by utilizing real-time sensor feedback (e.g., force transducers [136] and cameras [13]) to compensate for springback and geometric deviations [194]. Inadequate or inconsistent force application can result in undesirable outcomes such as incomplete forming or excessive material thinning, and therefore failure [52,124]. Fig. 19 shows the excessive thinning of a hollow component resulting from SPIF. The marked area of the component wall was thinned until failure. The recent research encompasses the integration of ML algorithms [78,288,290] that predictively adjust toolpaths to account for the mechanical deflection of actuators, thereby ensuring a seamless transition from design to finished components.

Fig. 19. Pyramidal test shape produced by SPIF [136].

5.2.3. Cost-effective tooling solutions for in-plane shearing

Reducing tooling costs while maintaining high precision and durability in the component being produced remains a critical challenge in manufacturing. Since tooling accounts for a significant share of overall production expenses, manufacturers constantly seek innovative solutions to extend tool life, reduce maintenance requirements, and lower initial investment costs. Due to the simplicity of the tooling in design, in-plane shearing is a particularly cost-effective method of producing sheet metal components.

In [14], the novel category of in-plane shear-induced sheet metal forming called “paddle forming” is introduced. This manufacturing

method is suitable for forming pronounced features such as beads in sheet metal components. Those features can serve as channels for cooling media or enhance the structural rigidity of larger sheet metal components. This can be achieved with a straightforward rotating tool. A rapidly rotating blade-shaped tool moves with minimal axial feed, creating a line contact between the tool and the workpiece to induce in-plane shear stresses. Fig. 20 (left) shows a sketch of the process. This incremental forming process induces high through-thickness shear strains in the workpiece, which have been experimentally shown to increase the permissible deformation before the onset of ductile instability. Fig. 20 (right) shows dimples in a 0.65 mm mild steel sheet. With this, the authors achieved a dimple height of 5.25 mm. This represents an improvement of around 30% compared to conventional forming. Experimental validation was conducted on various steel materials and the aluminum alloy AW5182. Among these, AW5182 exhibited the most significant enhancement in the Forming Limit Ratio. This approach allows for significantly higher deformation levels than conventional stretch forming processes. As shown in Fig. 20, a dimple can only be created using the rotating paddle. Complex and expensive forming tools are not required [14].

Fig. 20. Axis-symmetric male paddle forming (left), paddle formed dimple (right)[14].

ECAP is a severe plastic deformation technique used to produce ultrafine-grained materials [262]. Fig. 21 shows the materials processing principle. The process involves extruding a metallic billet through a die with two intersecting channels of identical cross-section. As the material passes through the intersection, defined by the internal channel angle and the outer curvature angle, it undergoes simple shear deformation. Maintaining the original cross-sectional geometry allows repetitive processing to accumulate plastic strain. Deformation is localized at the channel intersection, increasing dislocation density and forming misoriented grain boundaries, thereby

Fig. 21. Schematic of the ECAP process.

refining the microstructure. Microstructural evolution and homogeneity are governed by the processing route. Rotation of the billet between passes activates specific slip systems, enabling control of grain morphology [266,272].

To address the requirements for increased processing efficiency, several variants with advanced tooling have been developed.

Rotary-Die ECAP (RD-ECAP) [325] and Tri-RD-ECAP [210]: RD-ECAP employs a cylindrical die that rotates between cycles, thereby reducing processing time. Tri-RD-ECAP utilizes triaxial channels to facilitate continuous processing across multiple passes.

Vortex Extrusion-ECAP (Vo-CAP) [38] and twist channel angular pressing (TCAP) [186]: These hybrid methods superimpose torsional movement onto the shear deformation. This superposition increases the strain accumulation per pass, reducing the number of cycles required compared to standard ECAP.

In [91], a novel two-step press-forming technique specifically designed to mitigate fractures and wrinkles in automotive body parts is introduced, characterized by complex curvatures in the height direction. The integration of in-plane shear with longitudinal elongation enables the successful fabrication of complex geometries, such as front-side member rears, that are unachievable with conventional single-step forming due to ductility limits. By implementing an initial draw-forming process using strip blanks, the method induces in-plane shear deformation within the straight side walls. This pre-deformation effectively transforms the wall into a parallelogram, geometrically accommodating subsequent bending into a curved profile while significantly reducing the parasitic tensile and compressive stresses responsible for material failure. FEM analysis and experimental validation using ultra-high-strength steel demonstrate that the magnitude of the induced in-plane shear strain is primarily determined by the die geometry, specifically the punch radius and the differential material inflow distance.

In contrast to conventional ironing, where the rigid punch diameter remains constant during the retraction stroke, which leads to high interface pressure and therefore galling and tool wear, in [212], a novel adjustable punch concept featuring a hollow sleeve and an internal conical mandrel is proposed. This design enables the punch to elastically contract before withdrawal, effectively reducing the peak retraction force by up to 58% and the associated retraction work by over 50%, thereby significantly mitigating tool degradation. Furthermore, while conventional tooling lacks adaptability to material variations, this system enables micrometer-scale diameter adjustments via precise mandrel positioning. This provides a mechanism for active process compensation while maintaining geometric precision comparable to conventional solid-punch results.

Metal spinning is a well-established technique for creating rotationally symmetrical components from metallic materials [209]. Computer numerical control technology [75] allows for the production of complex, high-precision shapes used across industries such as aerospace manufacturing and household appliances. The process is formally defined in DIN 8584 as a tensile-compressive forming method that leverages the principles of in-plane shear deformation [161], especially in advanced variants.

As illustrated in Fig. 22, the standard configuration of a spinning process typically involves several key components. Spinning is a well-established incremental forming technique that transforms flat, typically axisymmetric sheet metal blanks (g) into hollow components (h). The process entails the application of pressure on the blank by means of a rotating mandrel (b) using a forming tool (e), which is typically a spinning roller or spinning wheel. This tool moves along arc-shaped paths (d) from the center outward, following the mandrel's contour. The mandrel, mounted on a spindle (a), defines the final part geometry, while the blank is clamped firmly using a tailstock (f). The blank is driven during rotation by frictional contact between the chuck and the pressure disc of the tailstock.

In contrast to the stamping or deep drawing processes, where thickness alterations frequently occur due to through-thickness

Fig. 22. Schematic view of a Spinning process. a) spindle; b) mandrel; c) counter holder; d) paths; e) tool; f) tailstock; g) sheet metal; h) component; i) trimming.

strain, the spinning process generally preserves the material thickness [139]. This is a further consequence of the in-plane shear-dominated stress state. In this context, the process achieves substantial shape changes with minimal risk of wrinkling or cracking, which is particularly advantageous for high-strength or low-ductility materials [170,310]. Furthermore, the low strain in the thickness direction reduces the likelihood of necking and enhances the formability of challenging alloys. Spinning can be conducted without a mold in specific process variants, enhancing flexibility.

A notable extension of this technique is flow forming, also called stretch spinning. As outlined in DIN 8583 Part 2, this method introduces compressive stresses along the axial direction to deliberately reduce wall thickness while maintaining or increasing length [152]. In this instance, the in-plane shear component significantly contributes to material flow and overall process efficiency. The deformation is concentrated around the point of contact with the clamping fixture. To mitigate the risk, it is recommended to arrange multiple spinning rollers symmetrically around the spindle axis. This will ensure force equilibrium and a more favorable stress distribution across several forming zones with the spinning roller, with the required forming forces being comparatively low. However, with high-strength or thick sheets, large asymmetric forces may arise, potentially causing the blank to slip. This configuration enhances both process limits and stability. The forming process is typically controlled by CNC systems, which precisely coordinate the movements of the mandrel and spinning roller [86]. Modern spinning machines often feature automatic tool changers and integrated workpiece handling, enabling flexible programming of multiple forming stages and increasing overall productivity. A counter-holder (c) is employed to prevent edge wrinkling, and final shaping is achieved through one or two finishing passes. Due to sheet anisotropy, lipping may occur at the workpiece edge; this can be corrected by trimming to ensure a uniform rim. In addition, various secondary operations, including trimming (i) and heat treatment, are becoming increasingly integrated into spinning systems.

6. Selected applications

This chapter takes up the topics described in the previous chapters and specifies them in the context of the industry and the

industrial manufacturing of typical components. This is done using one example from each of the out-of-plane and in-plane process categories. Fine-blanking is selected as the out-of-plane example because of its industrial relevance for the efficient manufacturing of functional surfaces, with the principles outlined in the paper actively applied. Ironing, which is currently gaining even greater industrial relevance for battery cell manufacturing, is the selected example of an in-plane shear-dominated process because it highlights the complexity of material modeling and numerical simulation.

6.1. Out-of-plane: fine-blanking of gears

With fine-blanking, ready-to-install components can be produced in a single stroke, except for any necessary deburring. Fine-blanking is characterized by a minimal die clearance (in the order of 0.5% of the sheet thickness), a special preparation of the die cutting edge, a counterpunch, and the v-ring on the die, and, depending on the application, a v-ring on the blank holder [125].

The axisymmetric 2D FEM simulation shown in Fig. 23a) shows the shear stresses of the 50% cut through sheet metal (6 mm, S420MC) during fine-blanking. The simulation outputs a mean stress triaxiality of -0.28 for nodes located within a circle with a radius of 0.5 mm centered on the die clearance at the level of the material still to be cut. The existing hydrostatic compressive stress state is superimposed on the shear stress of the material, whereby it is reasonable to assume that flow of the material can be maintained as a result. Fig. 23b) shows the material cut through to 75% material thickness. This results in a mean stress triaxiality of $+0.28$ in the area defined above in the material that has not yet been cut through. Here, the shear is now superimposed on a hydrostatic tensile stress state, which, in theory, leads to material failure in the form of tearing as soon as the material's flow capacity is exhausted. Fig. 24 shows the development of the equivalent plastic strain - triaxiality space for three selected points located in the center of the cutting clearance: point 1, 0.2 mm under the top surface of the sheet metal; point 2, in the middle plane; and point 3, 0.2 mm above the bottom surface of the sheet metal. The simulation is consistent with the descriptions of [151].

Fig. 23. Shear stresses during fine-blanking a) at a material separation of 50%, b) at a material separation of 75%.

Due to the special phenomena in fine-blanking described above and the potential of this process, it is still the subject of research. The many degrees of freedom, i.e., the geometries of the active elements in the tool or blank holder and counterpunch force profiles, enable not only high clean-cut portions, as a representative of geometrical properties, but also design options with respect to material-related properties, such as the residual stress state. Especially for near-net-shape blanking processes aimed at producing functional surfaces, this is a promising approach.

Fig. 24. Equivalent plastic strain - triaxiality development for three points located in the cutting clearance during fine-blanking until material separation.

It has already been shown that it is possible to manufacture precise power-transmitting gears with involute toothings by fine-blanking and to generate process-induced residual stresses on the functional surface. A fine-grained structural steel (S355MC) was used as the material. The idea of fine-blanking power-transmitting gears for specific applications holds untapped potential in terms of energy consumption and production costs compared to conventional manufacturing [206]. It was possible to generate specifically induced compressive residual stresses on the functional surface by fine-blanking using an involute pinion-wheel pairing, which presented a degree of difficulty s_2 . Switching to a different material (S500MC) demonstrated that the induction of compressive residual stresses is also applicable to higher-strength materials. The residual compressive stresses applied lead to a significant increase in the tooth root fatigue strength, i.e., the service life, about a gear damage criterion, which could also be increased as a result [217]. In addition to component improvements associated with the process-induced compressive residual stresses, it was also shown that no tears or cracks occurred on the functional surface at the measuring points (tooth tip, tooth flank, and tooth root) and that the die roll of power-transmitting involute gears is also geometry-dependent and decreases from the tooth tip via the tooth flank to the tooth root. The smooth cutting angles are close to the ideal of 90° . In addition, a high degree of precision was achieved for the gears' flanks and profiles, comparable to that of milled, case-hardened gears after grinding. It was also shown that the fine-blanked involute gears could run and were quieter than comparable conventionally manufactured gears.

6.2. In-plane: ironing

Ironing is selected as a representative case study for in-plane shear-dominated processes due to its industrial significance in the production of high-precision thin-walled components, such as beverage cans and battery housings. In this process, the wall thickness of a pre-drawn cup is intentionally reduced by forcing it through a clearance between the punch and the die that is smaller than the initial sheet thickness. Unlike conventional drawing, the mechanics of ironing are fundamentally governed by a localized deformation zone subjected to intense radial compression and redundant shear at the tool-material interface [245].

The complexity of the deformation mechanics is further illustrated through the FEM analysis presented in Fig. 25. The simulation highlights a critical phenomenon at the point of material thinning. The process involves severe through-thickness deformation that is often beyond the predictive capabilities of conventional shell elements in numerical simulations. Therefore, thick shell or solid elements are recommended to capture the ironing effect with sufficient fidelity [103].

As observed in the stress triaxiality distribution, the material points within the thinned region exhibit triaxiality values approaching zero. This transition from a compression-dominated state to a near-zero triaxiality confirms that the localized failure is driven by pure shear. Furthermore, the loading path analysis reveals that following this shear-dominated stage, triaxiality increases sharply, reaching or exceeding 0.33. This stage indicates a shift from shear localization to a tensile domination, where the material is essentially subjected to uniaxial pulling forces, eventually leading to the final tearing of the wall [15].

Regarding material behavior, the performance of ironing is highly dependent on how aluminum alloys, such as AA3004 and AA3104, respond to complex, non-proportional paths. While these alloys are commonly chosen for their high strain-hardening potential, their shear stability is sensitive to subtle variations in the yield surface shape and plastic anisotropy. A critical analysis of production data suggests that slight deviations in the hardening exponent (n -value) across batches can cause the "zero-triaxiality" zone to localize prematurely [245]. In high-speed production environments exceeding 300 parts per minute, these material fluctuations do not merely affect dimensions but fundamentally alter the failure limits, as the adiabatic heating localized in the shear zone can further reduce the material's resistance to the final tensile instability stage.

The tribological conditions at the tool-material interface are not merely a boundary constraint but a primary driver of the shear mechanics. The high normal pressures typical of ironing can cause the lubricant film to break down, especially when hard oxide layers are present. This breakdown shifts the stress state toward even more intense redundant shear, effectively "dragging" the material surface and accelerating the drop in triaxiality toward zero. Experimental strip reduction tests indicate that this transition to galling is a thermomechanical threshold [219].

Fig. 25. Stress triaxiality distribution extracted from an FEA of the ironing process.

Therefore, the prediction of surface defects and tool wear remains purely empirical and fails to capture the underlying physics of the process if the friction-induced shear component is not considered.

From a numerical perspective, accurately predicting ironing behavior and associated defects, such as shear fracture, requires advanced damage models and failure criteria. For example, in the case of high-aspect-ratio rectangular cups formed from AA3003 alloy, standard strain-based forming limits are insufficient due to the dominance of shear. Models such as the Generalized Incremental Stress State-dependent Model (GISSMO) coupled with a triaxiality failure diagram have been successfully applied to predict shear-induced failures under ironing conditions [148].

Future research should focus on developing path-dependent constitutive models that account for the rotation of the principal stress axes during the stroke. Moreover, integrating advanced tribological coatings and in-situ monitoring systems, such as piezoelectric sensors embedded in the ironing rings, offers a promising approach to detect the onset of galling in real time, transitioning from purely descriptive process design to a more robust, data-driven optimization of shear-dominated forming.

7. Summary and open topics

As a framework, this paper introduces inequality (1.1) to classify shear-dominated processes in the Lode parameter – stress triaxiality domain. Each metal forming process exhibits a distinct spatio-temporal pattern with respect to these quantities. The common theme for in-plane and out-of-plane shear-dominated processes is to stabilize and actively enforce the spatio-temporal pattern in the shear-dominated region, characterized by η_0 and $\bar{\theta}_0$ in Inequality (1.1). For many processes the target area even lies in the negative triaxiality half-plane to prevent a shift to the tension region leading to failure, which also applies to materials testing.

Different solutions to implement and control for the spatio-temporal pattern of the Lode parameter and the stress triaxiality have been proposed and transferred to processes: on the one hand through a priori geometrical manipulation of the workpiece (or specimen) and on the other hand through kinematic adaptations or active stress superposition during the forming process.

Shear-dominated processes in sheet metal forming are increasingly recognized for their unique material flow characteristics, enhanced formability, and capacity to enable novel manufacturing strategies [65]. Unlike conventional forming processes that are governed predominantly by tensile or compressive loading, shear-dominated processes offer distinct advantages, including lower forming forces and extended forming limits [18], which may be especially relevant for the processing of emerging materials, such as high-entropy alloys or metallic glass [274].

This chapter further outlines open research topics and methodological challenges regarding materials testing, modeling, and development of shear-dominated processes in sheet metal forming.

7.1. Gap in characterization methods

Despite the extensive development of shear-dominated material testing methodologies, current lab-scale experimental efforts remain predominantly focused on in-plane shear under plane stress conditions. This prevalence is largely driven by the accessibility of the testing devices as well as the necessity for stable and reproducible loading paths that facilitate incremental plastic deformation and reliable constitutive model calibration [48,174,251,328]. However, this experimental bias creates a significant disconnect from the deformation conditions encountered in many industrial forming processes.

In practical applications such as blanking, cutting, and shear localization, deformation is rarely confined to the plane stress state. Instead, it involves pronounced out-of-plane effects governed by 3D constraints, complex through-thickness stress evolution, and severe contact interactions. In these scenarios, shear deformation is frequently coupled with rapidly increasing stress triaxiality and elevated maximum principal stresses, particularly during the critical stages of localization and fracture initiation [141,167]. Consequently, unlike the strain-controlled accumulation in-plane tests, the failure mechanisms in out-of-plane-dominated processes are often stress-controlled. In addition, material anisotropic behavior in terms of both plasticity and fracture under in-plane and out-of-plane deformation can be an influencing factor in adapting the lab-scale in-plane findings to the out-of-plane

forming processes. New test innovations, as well as material models, particularly those that consider anisotropic fracture behavior, shall be a key focus to fill this gap.

An additional, largely underexplored challenge concerns the role of strain rate in shear-dominated deformation under out-of-plane constraints. Many out-of-plane processes occur at high strain rates, where thermal softening and adiabatic heating strongly influence localization and fracture [141]. In contrast, most shear tests are conducted under quasi-static or moderate strain-rate conditions, limiting their applicability to such scenarios. Bridging this gap will require the development of experimental and numerical approaches capable of capturing shear-dominated deformation under 3D constraints and high strain rate conditions. Bridging this gap is essential for enhancing the predictive capability of material models and ensuring they remain relevant to the complexity of industrial processes.

7.2. Shear cracks

A significant challenge remains the comprehensive understanding, characterization, and modeling of the influence of initial material conditions (microstructure, texture and anisotropy, residual stresses, edge quality) and pre-strain histories (including non-proportional loading, pre-damage, and strain gradients) on shear crack formation [111,146], which is especially relevant in forming process sequences.

Accurate experimental characterization of shear crack initiation and propagation under realistic forming conditions remains an open topic [143]. While advanced optical measurement techniques, particularly DIC, are increasingly utilized, they encounter limitations due to spatial resolution constraints and signal-to-noise trade-offs [110,111,121]. The fundamental understanding of shear crack formation mechanisms, including the complex interactions among stress triaxiality, the Lode parameter, strain rate, and temperature, is still ongoing [223].

Promising optical measurement techniques formulate the motion estimation problem, i.e., the identification of the displacement field, as a large optimization problem, which is solved in a joint way [29,114], which, for example, enables the decoupling of resolution from strain gauge length.

The investigation of microstructural statistics of shear crack mechanisms in sheet metal motivates 3D measurement strategies, for example, combining optical surface measurement techniques with high-energy micro-CT and digital volume correlation in representative edge volumes to connect microvoid and shear-band evolution to macroscopic crack paths [177], which seems especially realistic when microscopic shear cracks are opened via transverse loading before or during the analysis.

Modeling shear cracks under shear-dominated loading conditions remains challenging. Traditional FE methods, especially when utilizing element deletion techniques, often suffer from mesh dependency, numerical instabilities, and inaccuracies in capturing localized crack initiation and propagation [129]. The advancement and validation of non-local modeling methods, including gradient damage and phase-field fracture models, have shown promise in addressing these issues by incorporating length-scale parameters and accurately representing crack initiation and propagation without predefined paths [233,273].

Microstructure-informed modeling should be strengthened specifically for sheared edge conditions. Recent multi-scale and data-driven studies quantify how microstructural descriptors govern damage mechanisms in DP steels [87] and dual-scale FE frameworks already transfer punching-induced pre-strain into hole expansion simulations [226]. Embedding this microstructure sensitivity into nonlocal and phase-field fracture frameworks offers a route toward predictive shear crack modeling.

Nonetheless, these methods require further refinement, experimental validation, and approval of their reliability for practical engineering applications.

7.3. Adiabatic shear bands

Although the fundamental interplay between thermal softening and strain localization that results in ASBs is understood [102,318], translating this knowledge into process design and control remains challenging. One key element is the accurate experimental measurement and characterization of ASBs under realistic high-speed conditions. Traditional measurement methods encounter limitations due to the extreme strain localization and rapid temperature increases characteristic of ASBs [114]. Advanced techniques, such as high-speed DIC and infrared thermography, offer potential solutions that are currently implemented for in-plane shear [169,260] rather than the more process-relevant out-of-plane scenario. Further work on testing equipment that allows for a reliable capturing of strain, strain rate, and temperature fields of ASBs under industrially relevant process conditions is necessary [250,259].

Current constitutive and fracture models, such as the Johnson-Cook model or extended fracture criteria incorporating temperature and strain-rate effects [223,241], still struggle with accurately predicting the coupled thermo-mechanical behaviors inherent in ASBs under extreme deformation conditions. Robust numerical methods, including X-FEM, PFEM, and gradient-enhanced damage and phase-field fracture models, have shown promise [93,233,273], but require substantial validation with application-oriented experiments. Practical use of ASBs in industrial forming processes, such as in high-speed shear cutting, still faces significant technological hurdles to achieve the beneficial outcomes, such as reduced cutting forces, unique cut edge quality, or burr-free edges [313]. Dedicated equipment, such as specialized hydraulic presses or electromagnetic cutting devices, currently used to reach required high cutting velocities, introduces complexity and limits widespread adoption [239].

7.4. Residual stresses

A primary challenge remains the reliable prediction of the distribution of residual stress arising from complex shear deformation states, such as those encountered in blanking and fine-blanking. Current numerical models often inadequately account for the influence of specific process parameters, such as detailed tool geometry, material anisotropy, and frictional conditions, on residual stress formation [206,217]. This goes hand in hand with the experimental measurement of residual stresses. Although established techniques such as X-ray diffraction and hole drilling are widely used, their accuracy can be compromised in highly localized shear zones with significant stress gradients typical for blanked or sheared edges. Improved measurement methods capable of capturing the intricate spatial distribution and magnitude of residual stresses with high resolution and precision are crucial for model validation and process optimization [275].

Residual stresses and stress gradients are directly linked to hydrogen-induced delayed cracking and fatigue strength, underscoring the need for predictive, process-parameter-aware models [203,216].

7.5. Texture evolution

Current texture evolution models still struggle to capture the complex deformation paths of shear-dominated processes, such as ECAP, rolling, and incremental forming, particularly in materials with varied crystal structures [7,284]. Recent comparative work explicitly highlights that shear-dominated near-surface

loading is challenging for crystal-plasticity formulations, and that model-to-model differences become pronounced precisely in these regimes [54].

The experimental validation of texture models by traditional methods, such as X-ray diffraction and EBSD, effectively characterizes post-deformation textures. However, capturing dynamic texture evolution under high strain rates and large deformations remains technically demanding, because relevant texture changes can occur continuously and locally. In situ diffraction approaches are increasingly used to close this gap. In situ high-energy synchrotron diffraction has been demonstrated for tracking texture and twinning evolution under loading and reloading [89]. In situ neutron diffraction in shear geometries directly measures evolving texture and lattice strains under shear loading, providing validation data needed for the employed models [234]. Grain-resolved methods, such as high-energy X-ray diffraction microscopy, enable 3D, in situ orientation and texture evolution at the grain scale, which is particularly valuable for heterogeneous shear and path changes [37].

For high strain rates, time-resolved diffraction combined with dynamic loading has been demonstrated (including in-situ synchrotron X-ray diffraction at strain rates up to $\sim 2000 \text{ s}^{-1}$) [83], indicating both feasibility on the one hand and the need for more process-like out-of-plane shear configurations on the other.

7.6. Tooling and process control

Major issues are the effective management of elastic deformation and wear in tooling. High shear forces acting on tools induce significant bending moments and localized stresses, resulting in elastic deformation of punches and dies. Such deformation may lead to inaccuracies in component dimensions and edge quality, necessitating the development of enhanced tool designs.

Tool wear is critical due to the high local stresses and temperatures experienced in shear-dominated processes. Sliding wear, impact wear, and abrasion significantly degrade tool surfaces and adversely affect component quality. While wear-resistant tool materials and advanced surface treatments have improved tool longevity, optimizing these solutions for high-throughput industrial applications remains difficult [9]. In [56], it is explicitly highlighted that the durability of engineered tool surfaces remains a bottleneck and that solutions are needed, such as new tool materials, doped and multi-layer coating systems, better control of interface temperature via lubrication, self-repairing surface layers, and enhanced compressive stresses in the skin layer.

Especially regarding adhesive wear, promising results have been achieved in designing tailored coatings and tool materials for the processed sheet metal [237,238]. However, further research is required to explore the process-specific interactions between the different wear mechanisms and alternative tool materials, advanced surface engineering techniques, and novel lubrication approaches, including solid lubrication methods [205].

With reference to the conclusions in [56], current methods for tool and process monitoring, along with real-time control, integrating force sensors, eddy-current testing, optical measurement systems, and ML algorithms, have shown convincing results for monitoring tool wear and part quality in real time [213,258]. The use of softsensor methods [126] and AI [55] is increasingly enabling the incorporation of microstructural information in closed-loop control, and tool-workpiece-thermocouples enabled in situ, latency-free measurement of thermocouples as a basis for active compensation [278].

However, fully exploiting these technologies to predict and control the shear-dominated process, particularly in the transition region from negative to positive triaxiality values and under high-speed production conditions, remains critical [158].

7.7. Process optimization and development

Process optimization and development for shear-dominated sheet-metal forming processes offer significant opportunities. Characterized by lower forming forces compared to tensile or compressive-dominated processes, shear-dominated processes offer considerable opportunities for using smaller forming machines, reducing energy, and minimizing material consumption [14]. The intrinsic advantage of shear-dominated deformation to significantly improve material flow capabilities and delayed fracture initiation could enable the creation of complex geometries previously unattainable through other forming methods [18].

One of the primary open challenges is leveraging the sustainability potential inherent in shear-dominated forming processes. Referring to [12], many high-throughput metal forming processes, such as deep drawing, produce large portions of manufacturing scrap, because their mechanics require an extra perimeter for blank-holder restraint or addendum surfaces to keep the load path inside the operating window. This surplus is cut off after forming. Processes such as folding-shearing [65] intentionally use shear deformation after a folding step to minimize perimeter areas in sheet metal forming, thereby reducing manufacturing scrap. The general principle of creating a stiff structure followed by an in-plane shear-dominated process is a blueprint for further developments, i.e., a shift from boundary stabilization via clamped extra material to stabilization via tailored kinematics that induce localized shear.

In [297], different process routes are proposed for the manufacturing of metallic 3D structures. Especially taking into account property, specification, and manufacturing scrap [12], routes that incorporate shear-dominated processes excel. The localized and incremental nature of shear-dominated processes is a key enabler of material redistribution, enabling optimal design solutions with minimal material waste.

To fully exploit this potential, design pipelines must incorporate specific process limits and uncertainties, thereby opening perspectives for material understanding, tooling, and process control. Hence, realizations on high-throughput production scale depend directly on the enabling topics above. Here, the triaxiality and Lode parameter can be seen as guiding variables, not only for the design of new metal forming processes, but especially for the optimization of existing high-throughput manufacturing processes, for example, by stress superposition [286], or a recombination of existing processes in pre-stiffening and local forming sequences.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Wolfram Volk (1): Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mathias Liewald (2):** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **David Abedul:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Junhe Lian:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christoph Hartmann:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Supplementary materials

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